

AGNONYMS AND ARGONYMS

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Abstract: *People use different words to make their speech rich. For example: synonyms, antonyms, phrases, etc. As we know from our life, people use not only simple synonyms and antonyms that are understandable, but also some words that they hardly understand, i.e. slang, slang and argonyms are used as What do these actually mean and what do they mean.*

Keywords: *agnonyms, argonyms, pure, natural speech, speech of purity.*

First of all, let's talk a little about slang. The word slang is actually derived from the English word "slang" and is a variant of modern speech between a certain class of people that is not used in literary language. In some sources, argo is called the specific language of a certain professional or social group, meaning "dialect" from the French argot.¹

Often, slangs are called socially restricted words.² For example, the words used in the framework of "atarchi": yakan - "money", danap - "girl"; words used among railway observers: kachy - "inspector", kolkhoz - "passenger without a ticket". Some slangs are taken from the universal lexicon. But at such a time, these words are used in a different sense compared to the common language.

Agnonyms are words that are often used in human speech, but do not have a specific meaning. That is, people use such words a lot in their speech, they understand that this word means something in their speech, but what kind of meaning that word means, does not know the explanation. These words can be taken as bachelor, master, value, tik tok. Agnostic words can be found almost everywhere in everyday life. For example: "In social networks, the challenge is being continued with the 34th anniversary of the granting of the status of the state language to the Uzbek language and the holiday of the Uzbek language on October 21 under the hashtag of my mother tongue - my pride."³ The words

¹ Nilufar Rasulova. "Ona tilidan ma'ruzalar" Toshkent. "Nurafshon ziyo yog'dusi" 2017, birinchi kitob, 173-bet.

² Nargiza Erkaboyeva. "O'zbek tilidan ma'ruzalar to'plami". "Lesson press", Toshkent-2017. 143-bet

³ Farg'ona viloyat hokimligi telegram kanalidan

"hashtag" and "challenge" in the message received from this social network are anonymous words. Because these words enrich the text in some sense, we cannot understand or explain the specific meaning of these words. we can't.

Some people do not know the difference between slang and agnonym. Actually, both are different. We understood that slang is a modern speech between certain individuals in society, and its meaning in literary language expresses another specific meaning among individuals. Agonyms are a concept that does not have a clear meaning in human speech. That is the difference between the two.

In the 20th century, some lexical units in the Uzbek language began to "disappear". At the same time, they were not replaced by modern synonyms. This process caused the impoverishment of the Uzbek language. As a result, the stock of vocabulary has decreased significantly. This means that obsolete words are known only to some of the speakers, and this lexicon is "neighboring" with the group of agnomyms.

The term "agnonym" is derived from the Greek language and means "unknown, incomprehensible, unknown". An agnome is a lexical or phraseological unit of a language that is unknown, incomprehensible to the native speaker. Many agnomyms are found in dialect, special terms, or obsolete words (archaisms).⁴

In fiction, agnomyms perform a special aesthetic function. Agnomasia is the purposeful use of agnomyms in works of art in a certain style. The task of agnomasia can include reflecting the worldview of the heroes of the work and individualizing their speech. The agnomic units in the following passage are mainly used in the speech of a medical specialist (teacher's lecture) and have an illustrative character. The understanding of these lexemes is not so important for the student: "I sat down in the first row and opened my lecture notebook. Sadir Fuzaylovich walked calmly and continued his lecture. - Sleeping substances reduce the excitatory sessions in neurons, reduce the stimulating effect of the reticular formation on the cerebral cortex, and thus induce sleep.

I slowly turned and looked. Muzaffar was also sitting without taking his eyes off me. His beard has grown. His hair was not combed, his shirt was wrinkled... He would never walk like that. There was a conversation.

- The most effective drugs among sleeping pills, - Sadir Fuzaylovich raised his voice, - are barbiturates. Phenobarbital is currently the most

⁴ Qo'ldashev N. A. "Lingvoekologiya: til va nutq sofligining nazariy masalalari" doktorlik dissertatsiyasi. 2020.

powerful of these. This drug is taken as a hypnotic, convulsive, epilepsy - convulsive medicine in the form of powder or tablets of 0.1-0.2 grams..." (Otkir Hashimov. "Between Two Doors").

In the following text, we can observe that a comic situation arose as a result of the elder not knowing the meaning of the word bankruptcy: A young businessman called an elder living in the neighborhood to his house. Looking at the young man, whose house would soon be full of people, the father slowly asked:

"Yes, my child, peace?"

- Peace, father, peace. I became a little bankrupt. "Send a blessing to him," said the businessman.

"Amen, may you go bankrupt from now on," prayed the father!

In Abdulla Qahhor's work "Teacher of Literature", such agnomes as practicum, minimum, maximum, Detirding, Standing, Mering, Dumping served to individualize the speech of Baqijon Bagayev. This is how Bagijon Bagoyev embodies before our eyes the image of people who use words that others (even himself) do not understand.

Words that are unknown, unfamiliar, incomprehensible or poorly understood for those who communicate in a particular language are summarized under the name agnomys. Agnomys are an anthropocentric rather than a lingocentric phenomenon. That is, it can be considered as a phenomenon related to the linguistic ability of the language user. Experts believe that a certain lexical-phraseological unit must meet the following requirements in order to be accepted as an agnom:

1. If the speakers of the same language are completely incomprehensible, they exist at some level in consumption: jomish (jomish does not grow tall, goat runs and deer), olatoganok (alato "even if it's thick, it won't be like a thorn);

2. Heard but not fully understood by speakers of the same language: classification, bachelor, fauna, file, etc.

3. If the speaker is aware that a certain word belongs to a certain field, thinks that "only the people of a certain field know it", but could not tell clearly: histology, cystology, axiology, palsy, Esperanto, ethnography, anemia such as.

4. If the speaker knows that a certain word is an object, but cannot tell what it is: such as hantal, anguz, tuvoq, koshin, caffeine.

5. If the speaker knows the most general aspect of a particular word, but cannot tell its specific aspects: Sakura is a tree, but what kind of tree, where does it grow, and what is its shape? Sugur is an animal, but what kind of animal? Also, even if the user of the language uses a certain

word often and appropriately in the speech process, even if he does not know or cannot explain its meaning, this unit is considered an agnomin: spirituality, anqov, aqida, guya, qadiriya, Hamiyat, like a customer.

In conclusion, it can be said that anonyms are a negative phenomenon. They are the opposite of purity, which is the most important quality of speech. "The use of dark, that is, ambiguous words is unpleasant, like spots in the colorful, bright and expressive vocabulary of the language. They distort texts, make thinking difficult, and cause speakers and readers to draw false ideas and conclusions." That is why we should use pure, natural words in our speech as much as possible.

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